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Phrasal verbs and their characteristics

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ANNOTATION

Phrasal verbs and figures of speech are as often as possible utilized in ordinary English. They are moreover utilized in more particular dialect as counterparts for uncommon terms. The utilize of phrasal verbs and figures of speech by local patients and wellbeing care specialists makes their communication less demanding and less confounding. Non-native therapeutic specialists frequently come over with English phrasal verbs (figures of speech) in bona fide writings and communication. This article deals with semantic features of phrasal verbs. The collection of examples multi-words verbs is taken as a source of the article, where literal and idiomatic usage are studied.

KEY WORDS: multilingual speakers, conjugation, transitive, intransitive, separable, inseparable phrasal verbs

INTRODUCTION

Phrasal verbs are two or more words that together act as a completely new verb with a meaning separate from those of the original words. For example, pick up means to grab or lift, very different from the definitions. Popular in spoken English, phrasal verbs can be quite confusing because their definitions aren't always easy to guess—and there are thousands of them. In fact, many of the base verbs used to form phrasal verbs are used in multiple different phrasal verbs with distinct meanings, which can add to the confusion. For multilingual speakers, in particular, phrasal verbs are one of the most difficult topics in learning English. To help simplify this complicated subject, what follows is our guide to understanding English phrasal verbs, including a list of the most common ones.

What is a phrasal verb?

A phrasal verb combines a normal verb with an adverb or a preposition, referred to as the particle of the phrasal verb, to create an entirely new verbal phrase—the phrasal verb. The meaning of a phrasal verb is usually unrelated to the

meanings of the words that compose it, so think of a phrasal verb as an entirely new and independent word. When used in a sentence, phrasal verbs act the same as other verbs for conjugation and placement purposes, although they do have special grammatical rules regarding word order, which we talk about below. Phrasal verbs can be conjugated into every type of verb form, so you can use them anywhere you could use a normal verb. Let's look at the phrasal verb get over as an example. The verb get alone means to acquire, and the preposition over alone usually refers to being higher than or going above something. However, put them together and the phrasal verb get over means to recover from or overcome something, a completely new definition that's separate from the definitions of get and over. You can use get over just like a normal verb, in any form or tense. Here are some quick examples:

Simple past tense:

I had the flu last week but got over it.

Infinitive:

He wrote a song to get over his grandmother's death.

Gerund:

Getting over prejudice at work is never easy.

Past participle:

Having finally gotten over the breakup, they were ready to return their partner's things

How to conjugate phrasal verbs

When a phrasal verb is used as the main verb of a sentence, you conjugate the verb part and leave the other word or words as they are. Simply use whatever form of the verb you would use if it were alone.

I get up at noon during the summer.

However, this morning I got up at sunrise.

I have gotten up early too many times this month.

Notice how only the word get changes, while the word up remains the same. Also notice how get, an irregular verb, uses its irregular forms to fit whichever tense it needs. In this way, you can use phrasal verbs in all the verb tenses so that you're able to communicate anything you want. Conjugation is also important for maintaining verb tense consistency if you're using phrasal verbs in a list with other verbs. Types of phrasal verbs. To better understand phrasal verbs, it helps to organize them into two kinds of pairs: transitive and intransitive; separable and inseparable. A phrasal verb can belong to only one type within each pair (and all separable phrasal

verbs are transitive). **Transitive phrasal verbs.** Transitive phrasal verbs use a direct object, just like normal transitive verbs.

Charlie couldn't put up with the meowing cats any longer.

Intransitive phrasal verbs. Intransitive phrasal verbs do not use an object. The regional director was late, so the sales team went ahead without her. **Separable phrasal verbs.** With transitive phrasal verbs, you can sometimes put the direct object between the verb and the particle, as in "pick you up," for example. There are, however, a few rules to follow with separable phrasal verbs, so pay attention to our next section, about word order.

He forgot to shut the lights off before he left.

Inseparable phrasal verbs. Inseparable phrasal verbs cannot be split up; the verb and the particle must stay together. All intransitive phrasal verbs are inseparable.

The wayward son carried on without his father.

Some transitive phrasal verbs are also inseparable.

They went over the contract meticulously before signing it.

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